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 SURVEY

Long-Term Video QoE Assessment Studies: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT Although longitudinal studies are common in other disciplines, such as psychology, medicine, or User Experience, they are rarely used in Quality of Experience (QoE). However, observing users over time can provide useful information on the QoE and help to better understand its influencing factors. Here, we present a systematic review of the methodologies of longitudinal studies in the QoE domain. We review papers selected through a systematic search and discuss various aspects of described studies, such as methods of gathering subjective assessment or length of the studies. Our work recognizes common practices that can be used to reproduce and extend the proposed long-term study designs. Additionally, based on our review, we propose future work directions for the longitudinal QoE studies.

INDEX TERMS Quality of experience, longitudinal study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the research community is facing the so-called replication crisis in science [11], [14]. There are multiple examples of studies (e.g., pertaining to key studies within the field of psychology) that were not replicated, even though they use the same set-up [48]. An important implication of this fact is that one should not conclude based on a single study and take its result as ground truth. Instead, researchers should accumulate findings from multiple studies and draw conclusions by reviewing, aggregating, and comparing them. One of the ways to do this is to conduct a systematic review of the relevant literature.

to indicate solid findings as well as to detect those potentially under-powered or false.

In telecommunication technology, systematic reviews are not common. This is probably due to rapid changes and developments of technologies. We found a few examples of the systematic reviews of the Quality of Experience (QoE) or living labs studies [17], [18], [19]. As QoE measures the delight or annoyance of a customer's experiences with a service it is an important aspect, especially for service and network providers. However, to our knowledge, no systematic review scrutinizes longitudinal QoE studies. Such a systematic review is the key focus of this article. More precisely,